

DIVINFOOD

Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food

Deliverable D2.3

SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in processing and eating, and empirical data

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Executive summary

Neglected and underutilized crops (NUCs), historically integrated in traditional diets and well-adapted to local environments, have declined in use due to the dominance of high-yielding crops. Despite their marginal role in current agriculture, NUCs offer significant potential for sustainable, nutrient-rich, and climate-resilient food systems.

The DIVINFOOD project promotes the reconnection between NUCs raw material diversity and food diversity by employing mild processing techniques that preserve the integrity of traditional landraces. This approach supports healthier diets, adds value to local production, and creates economic opportunities for small-scale food processors.

To evaluate these benefits, the project proposes six SMART indicators: (1) type of processing, (2) research on processing, (3) creation of small processing businesses and jobs, (4) consumer reconnection with primary production and biodiversity, (5) diet nutritional value, and (6) attractive, healthier diets.

When evaluating each of these indicators, project initial results show mutual reinforcement between NUC use and the adoption of mild processing. DIVINFOOD has also enhanced existing research on minimal processing of NUCs, though big industrial interest often leans toward non-mild processing methods, creating a paradox when ultra-processed products use NUC-derived compounds. In various projects Living Labs (LLs), NUCs have supported the development of niche businesses aligned with consumer demand for healthy and traditional foods, while also beginning to attract larger-scale industrial interest.

Consumer awareness of agrobiodiversity was relatively low before the beginning of the project—only 39% of respondents in an EU survey could identify the plant species in their last meal—but DIVINFOOD initiatives are fostering a greater engagement. Through innovative and appealing NUC-based products, the project is demonstrating the potential of these crops to improve dietary diversity and sustainability.

In summary, with this Deliverable documenting and promoting SMART indicators, DIVINFOOD provides essential tools to support the broader adoption of NUCs and mild processing in Europe, benefitting both consumers and local food systems.

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1. General introduction on SMART INDEXES in DIVINFOOD

The use of genotypes (G) in food value chains is typically evaluated at the level of the agricultural plot, in relation to the biophysical environment and the agricultural practices implemented. DIVINFOOD extends the analysis of the benefits of using genotypes to the level of the food value chains considered in the Living Labs, and, when possible, at the level of the region/country.

Furthermore, the use of genotypes in food value chains is typically assessed through agronomic and technological criteria, so that the benefits of using genotypes are essentially measured through indicators related to productivity (e.g., yield) and technological quality (e.g., protein rate). The DIVINFOOD project assumes that using genotypes generates a larger range of benefits, not reduced to the criteria and indicators which are promoted in the agro-industrial system.

The DIVINFOOD approach thus broadens the analysis of genotype-environment interactions, both from the point of view of the environment considered and the results measured. The classic equation **GxE = yield and technological quality**, where G = genetically homogeneous cultivars, and E = biophysical environment and agricultural practices, is here extended to **GxE = ecosystem services + other benefits + costs**, where G = a diversity of genetic resources (pure lines, populations, landraces, etc.) and E = biophysical environment, agricultural practices, processing techniques, marketing channels, social organisations and regulations.

Finally, the impacts of genotype use are typically evaluated through indicators measured using tools available in the laboratory (e.g., NIRS method to assess grain quality) and in relation to the objectives promoted in the agro-industrial system (yield maximisation, technological parameters for industrial processing). DIVINFOOD seeks to evaluate these impacts through SMART indicators which can be measured, as far as possible, by easy-to-use methods. SMART indicators are specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound indicators that are used in monitoring and evaluation; they help to ensure that the indicators chosen are well-defined and can be effectively measured to track progress towards specific goals.

In the DIVINFOOD project, the specific goals are, on one hand, to develop healthy plant-based foods and environmentally, economically and socially sustainable food systems. On the other hand, the goal is to support professionals, policy-makers and citizens in evaluating by themselves, as far as possible, the impacts of using genotypes (i.e. growing a certain type of cultivar, e.g. population vs pure line of a certain type of crop, e.g. rivet wheat instead of common wheat). Doing this, will facilitate the collective management and monitoring of agrobiodiversity. The indicators and measurement methods must therefore be chosen in relation to these goals.

In the field of agrobiodiversity, DIVINFOOD targets genotypes related to neglected and underutilised crops (NUCs). NUCs are those to which little attention is paid, or which are entirely ignored by agricultural researchers, plant breeders and policy makers (Padulosi et al., 2002¹). The neglect of NUCs is partly due to their low competitiveness compared with major crops, so that

¹ Padulosi S, Hodgkin T, Williams JT, Haq N (2002) Underutilized crops: trends, challenges and opportunities in the 21st Century. In: Engels JMM, Rao VR, Brown AHD, Jackson MT eds. Managing plant genetic diversity. Wallingford, UK: CABI Publishing; Rome: International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPGRI).

they have not attracted the interest of those involved in the agro-industrial system. In this sense, NUCs are giving rise to alternative environments to the agro-industrial environment for the use of genotypes. The DIVINFOOD project aims to highlight the benefits associated with interactions between NUC genotypes and these alternative environments, throughout the value chains considered in the LLs and at regional/country level. The objective is to propose SMART indicators to measure these benefits and to provide empirical data relating to these indicators.

A set of complementary deliverables presents SMART indicators, and empirical data, related to the benefits resulting from the interactions between NUC genotypes and their environment of use in breeding (D4.3), cultivation (D3.5), food processing and eating (D2.3), and marketing (D1.4). All data are recorded in the GxE database developed in WP5. Depending on the value chain stages, the proposed SMART indicators will not be fully measured in the time allotted to DIVINFOOD, but they are designed to be used by the actors involved in the field to evaluate and manage their activity around NUCs, and to compare the benefits gained from the use of these NUCs with those generated by major crops.

This deliverable D2.3 is part of this set of deliverables and presents the SMART indicators and empirical data, related to the benefits, for the value chains considered in the LLs and for their regions/countries, of using NUC genotypes in processing and eating. For each SMART indicator, 2 steps of measurement will thus be proposed: STEP1, at the level of the value chains considered in the LLs, and STEP2 at the level of a region (which could be the LL region, the country, etc.). While the completion of step 1 will provide empirical data to be used in the project, the formalisation of step 2 will provide concrete support for stakeholders and policy-makers to assess the benefits of using agrobiodiversity at the level of a region (for instance, in relation with the agricultural/food policies which have been implemented at this level), and will be mobilised in the project WP5 to formulate recommendations. This fine-tuning of the two measurement levels was first developed and tested in WP4 and then applied to other WPs, what explains the three-month delay in the submission of this deliverable linked to WP2. Nevertheless, these interactions between WP2, 3, 4 and WP5 database were very useful to develop a systemic approach of NUCs use.

A final remark concerns the use of the term 'indicator', rather than the term 'index' mentioned in the DoA. The use of 'index' in the DoA was based on the idea that an index is intended to be easy to understand and useful for stakeholders (e.g. consumer price index). However, an index is also often understood as the synthesis of several indicators, which can ultimately limit its appropriation. We therefore finally opted for the term indicators, better understood by the living lab partners, even if some SMART indicators developed in the project are made up of several sub-indicators and therefore can still be considered as indexes.

2. Background: relevance of mild processing and eating NUCs

Many neglected and underutilized crops (NUCs) were used as traditional foods for centuries, with good adaptation to local environment, but became increasingly neglected when more productive crops became available in farming systems. Although they play a minor role in current farming and food systems, their incorporation into farming systems could lead to nutrient-dense, climate-resilient, and sustainable agriculture, as well as to the improvement of the dietary diversity contributing for a healthier diet (Li et al., 2020²).

In Work Package 2, the DIVINFOOD project explores the potential health, socio-economic and environmental benefits of increasing the processing and eating of two types of neglected and underused crops (NUCs): locally produced non-soy legumes and minor cereals. Increase intake of legumes, rich in plant-based proteins, may contribute to reduce meat consumption, while minor cereals, potentially more digestible than common wheat, could support the development of low-gluten products for individuals with gluten sensitivity. These crops besides aligning with the growing demand for healthy, plant-based diets, provide also important ecosystem services, including nitrogen fixation, soil fertility enhancement, support for pollinators, and habitat for birds, thereby addressing in addition consumers concerns about environmental sustainability.

Healthy diets have an optimal caloric intake comprising a diversity of plant-based foods, low amounts of animal source foods, unsaturated rather than saturated fats, and limited amounts of refined grains, highly processed foods, and added sugars (Willett et al. 2019³).

While consumers show willingness to adopt healthy plant-based products derived from NUCs, there remains a gap between minor cereals and underused legumes and their integration into appealing, healthy, and nutritious food products or recipes. In DIVINFOOD we hypothesize that such barriers can be addressed through the development of mild or minimal processing approaches. Contrary to ultra-processing approaches, **'mild' or 'minimal' processing** is often described as treating the agricultural raw material 'as little as possible, but as much as necessary', to preserve or enhance nutritional and sensory quality and guarantee editability, palatability and food safety. Thus, the idea behind mild processing is to retain most of the inherent physical, chemical, sensory and nutritional properties of agricultural produce (AGROVOC 2022⁴, Alzamora

² Li X, Yadav R, Siddique KHM (2020) Neglected and underutilized crop species: The key to improving dietary diversity and fighting hunger and malnutrition in Asia and the Pacific. *Frontiers in Nutrition* 7:593711. doi:10.3389/fnut.2020.593711.

³ Willett W, Rockström J, Loken B, Springmann M, Lang T, Vermeulen S, Garnett T, Tilman D, DeClerck F, Wood A, Jonell M, Clark M, Gordon LJ, Fanzo J, Hawkes C, Zurayk R, Rivera JA, De Vries W, Majele Sibanda L, Afshin A, Chaudhary A, Herrero M, Agustina R, Branca F, Lartey A, Fan S, Crona B, Fox E, Bignet V, Troell M, Lindahl T, Singh S, Cornell SE, Reddy S, Narain S, Nishtar S, Murray CJL (2019) Food in the Anthropocene: the EAT–Lancet Commission on healthy diets from sustainable food systems. *Lancet* 393:447–92. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31788-4.

⁴ AGROVOC (2022) Minimally processed foods. AGROVOC Multilingual Thesaurus. Accessed 7 March 2023.

et al. 2016⁵, Fardet 2018⁶, Hotz & Gibson 2007⁷, Montero et al. 2016⁸, Sibbel 2007⁹, Siro et al. 2008¹⁰).

Examples of mild processing are removal of inedible or unwanted parts, drying, crushing, grinding, milling, fractioning, filtering, roasting, boiling, pasteurisation, refrigeration, freezing, placing in containers, vacuum packaging, or non-alcoholic fermentation.

The DIVINFOOD project aims to reconnect food diversity with raw material diversity, by employing minimal or mild food processing methods and formulations that preserve the integrity of raw materials, therefore enhancing the expression of landraces and local varieties' potential. Targeted products include: dairy alternatives (e.g., yoghurt and cheese) from lupine, ancient eastern world type fermented products such as Tempeh and Miso made from grass pea, intended for incorporation in higher protein biscuits, pasta or bread, and cereal-based products (e.g., bread, pasta, muesli) formulated with ancient cereals whose gluten profiles seem to be better tolerated by sensitive individuals. These processing approaches not only support the development of nutritious and appealing plant-based foods that can improve dietary quality but also generated economic and social benefits by enabling market differentiation of small-scale processors and strengthening links to local production systems.

3. Why propose indicators in relation to the benefits of NUCs mild processing and eating?

Developing SMART indicators for assessing the benefits of mild processing and eating of NUCs is essential for promoting their adoption among both processors and consumers, and their support by policies. In DIVINFOOD, these indicators are supposed to highlight and discuss the benefits of mild processing and eating NUCs in terms of food security, sustainability, and dietary diversification.

One big challenge in NUCs adoption/eating is their limited use by processors. From DIVINFOOD Living Labs (LL) experience it was clear that this is mostly due to their insufficient availability in national markets, that leads to a lack of consistency in supply, complicating processing requirements. On the other hand, due to small-scale availability there are higher associated production costs, but room for innovation and opportunity of development for small-scale farmer-processors and food companies as NUCs are of no/low interest for big players.

⁵ Alzamora SM, et al. (2016) Minimally Processed Foods. In Encyclopedia of Food and Health pp. 767-771. Elsevier.

⁶ Fardet, A (2018) Characterization of the degree of food processing in relation with its health potential and effects. *Advances in Food Nutritional Research*, 85:79-129.

⁷ Hotz C & Gibson RS (2007) Traditional food-processing and preparation practices to enhance the bioavailability of micronutrients in plant-based diets. *Journal of Nutrition*, 137(4):1097-1100.

⁸ Monteiro C, Cannon G, Levy RB, et al. (2016) The star shines bright. *World Nutrition*, 7:28-38.

⁹ Sibbel A (2007) The sustainability of functional foods. *Social Sciences and Medicine*, 64:554-61.

¹⁰ Siro I, Kapolna E, Kapolna B, Lugasi A (2008) Functional food. Product development, marketing and consumer acceptance-a review. *Appetite*, 51:456-67.

When we think about consumers the other big challenge in NUCs adoption/eating is consumer low awareness and low consumption. This might be caused by limited knowledge on NUCs and on their benefits, or because it is difficult to find NUC products in markets. Then when consumers find them, there might be a lack of familiarity with their most optimal cooking methods, leading to negative perceptions of taste and convenience, particularly in more traditionally time consuming and complex processed forms.

SMART indicators can guide small-scale processors in adopting NUCs by highlighting that innovative mild processing techniques preserve the nutritional and sensory quality of NUCs, maintain a connection to the raw material and traditional flavours, and offer cost-effective solutions suitable for small-scale operations. Finally, they can also guide small-scale processors to increase NUCs market appeal through innovative, yet simple processing methods.

There is indeed a strategic importance not only of processing but also of consuming NUCs, since by encouraging the consumption of locally produced climate-resilient NUCs, it will reduce dependence on imports and enhance agroecological benefits (e.g., nitrogen-fixing legumes) (developed in WP3, see Fruzsina et al. 2025¹¹). This will support the local economies, at the same time that supports healthier diversified diets and strengthen the regional food heritage.

By addressing these challenges through SMART indicators, policy-makers, researchers, and food processors can develop evidence-based strategies to support the processing and eating of NUCs, by ensuring their long-term viability and acceptance.

4. NUCs mild processing and eating landscape in Europe

The process of construction of “SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in processing and eating, and empirical data” has been inspired by the work done in WP4 (see Lazzaro et al., 2025¹²) and started by the development of a questionnaire sent to all the DIVINFOOD partners involved in “WP2: Co-produce new and diversified healthy plant-based products and recipes”. **This questionnaire** was meant to compile all the benefits identified by the different stakeholders within the different LLs, associated with mild processing and consumption of NUCs and **allowed us to grasp an overview of the European landscape on NUCs mild processing and eating.**

Not only quantitative (preliminary data from DIVINFOOD related experimental activities) but also qualitative data (like verbatims, defined as the statements or responses from any of the involved stakeholders, using exactly the same words as were originally used) were collected with this

¹¹ Szira F, Fekete KA, Desoutter L, Loconto AM, Clair D, Colombo L, Lazzaro M, Vaz Patto MC, Wallman D, Bertelsen I, Veér Z, Horváth J (2025). Deliverable D3.2 - Report on NUCs agronomic performances in specific environments of the first selected varieties (season 1&2) (Version V3). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14783203>

¹² Lazzaro M, Annicchiarico P, Bencze S, Chiffolleau Y, Desoutter L, Desclaux D, Krier M, Makankubana D, Robin M-H, Szira F, Tedesco J-F, Vaz Patto MC, Wallmann D, Wurtz A (2025). Deliverable D4.3 - SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in breeding, and empirical data (Version V5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15109841>

questionnaire. The SMART indicators privileged in this deliverable are expected to be easy to measure.

The questions posed were:

1. Do you think that processing/using/adopting NUCs will encourage the use of mild processing?
2. Do you think that processing/adopting NUCs is an opportunity to foster research on mild processing?
3. Do you think processing/adopting NUCs is an opportunity to maintain or even create small business and jobs in your LL?
4. Do you think that processing NUCs is an opportunity to reduce processing costs?
5. Do you think that eating NUCs is an opportunity to reconnect consumers with the region where the food is coming from? Or to the agricultural systems? Or to the primary production? Or to cultivated biodiversity?
6. Do you think that eating NUCs is an opportunity to improve the nutritional value of diets? Or to diversify diets? Or to develop healthier eating habits?
7. Do you think that eating NUCs is an opportunity to make the consumption of healthier diets (due to more legumes or more minor cereals on it) more attractive?
8. What other benefits of mild processing/eating minor cereals and legumes, have you heard about at conferences with professionals, festivals with consumers, etc?

As a core component of the project, mild processing methods—both traditional and innovative—for neglected and underutilized crops (NUCs) are implemented in DIVINFOOD LLs. This orientation is driven by the ease of processing, suitability for small-scale applications and shorter value chains, and enhancement of specific quality and sensory attributes. While not all LLs focus on mild processing research, they acknowledge NUC adoption as a catalyst for such studies. Among LLs engaged in this research—primarily optimizing fermentation techniques for legume NUCs—emerging findings reinforce the benefits of mild processing in preserving the functional, sensory, and nutritional quality of NUCs raw material.

Neglected crops possess untapped potential for niche markets due to their unique nutritional and organoleptic properties. All Living Labs recognise that NUC adoption can support small businesses and job creation. Established LLs already demonstrate this through agri-food enterprises that process NUCs, diversifying product portfolios via mild processing innovations. However, NUC processing is not widely seen as a means to reduce processing costs, as limited production volumes impede to implement an economy of scale.

Most Living Labs view NUC consumption as a way to reconnect consumers with primary production and cultivated biodiversity. However, consumer appreciation varies. Significant promotion and education efforts are still needed for specific NUCs. Successful initiatives in established LLs, which have linked traditional crops to cultural heritage, demonstrate the potential to enhance biodiversity awareness while promoting dietary diversification.

Living Labs agree that consuming legume NUCs supports healthier diets by replacing animal proteins with plant-based sources and promoting dietary diversification. However, processing levels are crucial; mild processing can enhance nutritional value by reducing antinutritional factors (as confirmed for some legume NUCs in the project), while ultra-processing with excessive additives diminishes nutritional quality.

Consumer aversion to NUCs appears stronger for legumes than cereals, often due to negative experiences or stereotypes. However, project LLs demonstrated that these barriers can be overcome through innovative mild processing, co-developed with chefs and catering professionals to enhance taste — the primary driver of consumer choice. Information campaigns highlighting NUCs' unique flavours, cultural significance, and health benefits can further boost acceptance. Moreover, regular legume NUC consumption naturally mitigates potential adverse effects.

5. Indicators related to NUCs mild processing and eating

	Indicators	Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Relevant	Time-bound
1	Type of processing	-	++	++	+	+
2	Research on processing	+	++	++	++	+
3	Creation of small processing business and jobs	-	+	+	+	+
4	Consumers reconnection with primary production and biodiversity	-	+	+	++	+
5	Diet nutritional value	+	++	++	++	+
6	Attractive healthier diets	+	+	++	++	+

Table 1. Summary table of the proposed indicators

For each indicator, we will present:

- what is valued with this indicator;
- how to measure it, considering 2 steps;
 - i) STEP1, consisting in measuring the indicator within the LL, in relation to DIVINFOOD's activity;
 - ii) STEP2, in which the indicator can be measured in the LL region/country by concerned institutions, NGOs, consumer associations, etc.
- empirical data through examples from the DIVINFOOD Living Labs.

5.1 Type of processing

What is valued:

Mild processing

How to measure:

STEP1:

- YES/NO at the LL level
- ratio between the number of NUCs-based food made with mild methods in the LL and the total number of NUCs-based food made in the LL
- ratio between the number of food processing units using mild processing methods for NUCs in the LL and the total number of food processing units processing NUCs in the LL

STEP2: same ratios, but at the level of the LL region/country

References:

Jones SK, Estrada-Carmona N, Juventia SD et al. (2021) Agrobiodiversity Index scores show agrobiodiversity is underutilized in national food systems. *Nature Food* 2:712–723. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00344-3>

Examples from DIVINFOOD Living Labs for Encouraging Mild Processing Through NUC Adoption

Hungary (LL LegHung and LL CerHung)

Legume-based products in Hungarian stores (e.g. legume pasta, legume crisps and other snacks, etc.) are growing in popularity, however most of them, which are imported and/or made from legumes grown outside of the country, have not been produced with mild processing techniques. Nevertheless, for those grown in the LL LegHung, mild processing is the most used method, as these legumes are sold in bulk, after a simple drying process.

ACC, which is a consumer association in Hungary, organised several NUCs tastings with consumers in the Hungarian LLs. First, Hungarian whole dry seeds (lentil and chickpea) and split seeds (pea) and not more processed than drying, were sent to consumers. Regarding cereal NUCs, the samples sent were mild processed whole grain pasta (from emmer, einkorn, spelt) from Hungary. Consumers received information on the NUCs and needed to participate on a webinar presenting the ways to cook them. In February 2025, ACC organised an open event about Cereal NUCs and sourdough and sourdough bread making as a mild processing preparation. Thirty-four people participated in the workshop. After this event, 200 people got the NUC sourdough bread recipe through their newsletter.

Grain milling might be the oldest manufacturing process in the world, and many techniques are currently used in the cereal food industry. The two predominant methods used in wheat milling are stone milling and roller milling. In this context stone milling can be considered as mild processing technique and has a few, clear advantages: easy to use and the simplicity of the system; higher concentrations of macroelements, microelements, and polyphenols in flour; increased whole wheat bread volume; popularity with consumers and suitability for small-scale processing (Capelli et al. 2020)¹³. In the LL Cer-Hung both farmers and millers listed on the 'map of actors' expanded in DIVINFOOD by ÖMKi are using stone-milling: <https://biokutatas.hu/tudastar/gazdamolnar-pek/>

Additionally, these actors proposed good quality sourdough bread which was made from a mild process compared to industrial/yeast based bread, and was based on good quality flour. It seems simple, but getting the right quality and quantity of flour is not. This is why it is particularly important that the various players in the bread industry can get to know each other better, share their experiences and needs, and receive the latest research findings. To this end, the map developed by ÖMKi also includes dehullers and bakers.

France (LL BeanLyon and LL CerOcc)

In the LL BeanLyon, the meat bean was not processed before DIVINDOOD as it was not grown anymore, but in the LL, common bean was classically processed with simple methods (drying, canning). The project introduced both meat bean and new mild processing techniques.

One of the processors, an innovative one, produced for the very first-time bean flour and so a meat bean flour was born. Next target is to offer this flour to pastry chefs in order for them to create recipes. First feedback from the mill processor was that meat bean flour is "easy to make", delivering a "very white colour" and a texture similar to wheat flour. Another processor will develop cooked meat bean in glass jar. The target in this case will be to set up the right process. These first mild processing trials with the NUC encourage to continue tests with potential consumers who could start using it through the different recipes being set up by the chefs.

A researcher at an engineering school within the LL CerOcc suggested that the use of NUCs does not specifically lead to the implementation of mild processing, especially in the case of the work developed with einkorn and rivet wheat. However, what can be seen is that people who already use mild processing are more likely to use NUCs. For example, bakers who already used mild processes and prefer slow fermentation methods with bread wheat also tend to use old or little-used species or varieties. The use of NUCs or the introduction of mild processes seems to depend more on the ethics of the processors and farmer-processors.

Portugal (LL GPeaPort)

In the Portuguese region of Alvaiázere, grass pea was already processed through diverse traditional mild processing ways. After seed drying, grass pea is normally consumed boiled in dishes like chicharada (grass pea stew), or in delicious pastry (together with wheat flour, sugar

¹³ Cappelli A, Oliva N, Cini E (2020) Stone milling versus roller milling: A systematic review of the effects on wheat flour quality, dough rheology, and bread characteristics, Trends in Food Science & Technology, 97:147-155, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2020.01.008>.

and eggs), or in very appreciated liquors. The DIVINFOOD project introduced fermentation in the LL, generating a new use of mild processing techniques.

Fermentation improved the sensorial attributes. For example, during an informal sensorial appreciation test made with lab collaborators (n=4), the delightful chocolate and the roasted nuts odour of the fermented grass pea (miso) were mentioned.

As fermentation was not used before DIVINFOOD, the Portuguese team conducted two training sessions, one on grass pea Miso and another on grass pea Tempeh preparation, involving the local small-scale processors, opening the way for a diversification of grass pea food products obtained through mild processing.

In addition, the traditional grass pea farmers from Alvaiázere region in Portugal agreed on the grass pea's fermentation as a possible solution to introduce grass pea seed byproducts on the market, reducing profit loss.

Italy (LL LegItSwitz)

Mild processing was clearly the key option for the LegItSwitz LL farmers/processors who debitter grain to get lupin in brine, hummus or other creams. Mild processing can also be considered for lupin-based pasta, as milling and pasta making do not imply invasive technological solutions. The same applies to fermentation for which tests are being carried out in the Italian part of the LegItSwitz LL.

The Italian part of the LegItSwitz LL is collaborating with two companies: the one specialised on fermentation is not yet working on lupins and will make tests in the near future; the one with reputed trade-mark is collaborating with a food company on a salty snack recipe blending lupins with wheat flour. This latter company processes foodstuff both through mild but also 'hard' processing. The lupin-based snack will be tested soon through e-commerce and feedback will be collected among buyers/consumers through surveys.

Switzerland (LL LegItSwitz)

Before DIVINFOOD and LUPINNO SUISSE (another project developed in this LL), a very few processors already used lupin in their products, especially in dairy and meat alternatives. However, in these cases, the raw material used was imported lupin in a highly processed format (such as isolates, concentrates).

During LUPINNO SUISSE, some application trials were conducted with 5 Swiss food processors of different sizes (2 food industries and 3 SMEs). In all cases, applied processed were mild in order to preserve the functional or nutritional benefits of white lupin: houmous, fermented products, lupin in brine.

In the past 2 years, we could also observe a trend towards roasted lupin as a local and sustainable alternative to coffee, which supports the hypothesis that NUC could encourage the use of mild processing.

Both in Italy and Switzerland, the project introduced mild processing techniques for lupins, calling for the evaluation of the indicator in step 2.

To conclude for this indicator, the hypothesis that using NUCs adoption encourages mild processing techniques seems positive in STEP1, while the opposite seems also possible (the adoption of mild processes encourages the adoption of NUCs). This calls to assess the indicator in STEP2 in the next years, that will also contribute to measure the impact of the project.

5.2 Research on processing

What is valued:

Research on mild processing

How to measure:

STEP1:

- YES/NO
- Ratio between the number of scientific studies/researchers/research organisms on mild processing techniques for NUCs in the LL and the total number of scientific studies/researchers/research organisms in the LL

STEP2: same ratios, applied to the LL region/country

Examples from DIVINFOOD Living Labs on fostering research on mild processing through NUCs adoption

Portugal (LL GPeaPort)

In the GPeaPort LL, fermenting grass pea opened new lines of research, namely on the chemical characterisation of the new food products developed based on this innovative mild processing and its functionality in the human health. In this context, in Portugal, miso and tempeh made with the fermented grass pea were characterized for their phytochemical composition, e.g., total phenolic compounds, saponins, trypsin inhibitors, beta-ODAP, and nutritional content in terms of amino acid content. This on-going work makes part of a Master thesis defended in 2025.

Italy (LL LegItSwitz)

CREA started to research into fermented lupin dairy-like and minimally-processed flour-based products. However, being lupins very rich in protein content, research and industrial interest was also attracted by extrusion and other non-mild processing options, to enrich plant-based food products for which the market is showing a potential.

In this direction, if and when lupins will be valued at industrial level they may quit their artisanal status, which is providing identity to the crop, and become a raw material prone to any sort of processing. This should be considered as a risk in popularising lupins vis-à-vis consumers and

industry as they may be more attracted by the healthiness of the end products or their composition, rather than by the way they are processed.

Switzerland (LL LegItSwitz)

In terms of food processing, areas of interest were driven by the market demand for vegetarian/vegan options. The research topics included different processing levels regardless of the crops. For example, protein extraction is still explored on major and minor plant-protein crops. The protein content of a crop and its availability on the market will drive R&D in the agri-food sector. The focus is then more on ways to reduce the environmental footprint of the extraction process than on studying mild processing.

However, more and more food companies are interested in healthier and more sustainable options which means shorter ingredient lists and mild processing. This is where NUCs could play a role if a major crop cannot deliver the expected and required properties. This calls for the evaluation of the indicator in STEP2.

France (LL CerOcc)

The growing demand for einkorn-based bread by gluten-sensitive consumers encouraged the development of research on mild processing of einkorn, and on its impacts on gluten quantity and quality in the LL CerOcc. DIVINFOOD enabled to increase research efforts on mild processing, calling to evaluate the indicator in STEP2.

To conclude, regarding this indicator, in the considered LLs, research on minimal processing of NUCs was in some cases developed before DIVINFOOD but DIVINFOOD strengthened the research effort. However, research into NUCs industrial processing is also driven by market-demand, leading to paradoxes when NUCs protein isolates feed ultra-processed food while consumers demand 'healthy food'. This calls to evaluate the indicator in STEP2, in the next years.

5.3 Creation of small processing businesses and jobs

What is valued:

The creation or maintenance of small processing businesses and jobs through the use of NUCs

How to measure:

STEP1:

- YES/NO
- Ratio between the number of new and existing small-scale processing companies using NUCs and the total number of new and existing food companies in the LL, compared with the ratio between the number of new and existing small-scale

processing units using major crops and the total number of new and existing food companies in the LL

STEP2 – same ratios, applied to the LL region/country

Examples from DIVINFOOD Living Labs on maintenance or creation of small businesses and jobs through the adoption of NUCs mild processing

Hungary (LL CerHung and LL LegHung)

According to the consumer surveys conducted by ACC, there is an opportunity to create small businesses to develop legume-based convenient food (e.g. canned legumes, ready-made products like store-bought hummus or falafel, etc.) or gluten-free products whose demand is expanding.

For small-scale stakeholders involved in the LegHung LL, NUCs only represented a very small parts of their sales (< 5%). Small-scale restaurants and chefs are experimenting with incorporating legume-based recipes into their menus: the success is still limited but growing. This calls to assess the indicator in STEP2, to evaluate how using legumes helped these restaurants to develop and maintain in a context of growing demand for both healthy and gluten-free products.

France (LL CerOcc)

In the CerOcc LL the use of NUCs enabled farmers to diversify their activities and get more added value from einkorn or rivet wheat compared with common or durum wheat when sold in short and mid-tier chains. DIVINFOOD strengthened this dynamic by enabling bulgur and pasta processing and testing different varieties. It also supported knowledge sharing with, and between small-scale businesses.

Portugal (LL GPeaPort)

Grass pea mild processing is maintaining and creating new jobs in the Alvaiázere region with small bakery, pastry, liquors and restauration business founded on this NUC mild processing. Some of these businesses reinvented themselves through innovative mild processing of grass pea, and some are completely new offering differentiated products. At a more national level, mild processing can create opportunity for the development of legume-based probiotics, which is an unexplored business at least in Portugal, and for the expansion of grass pea (NUC) in the food market at a national level.

Italy (LL LegItSwitz)

Lupins present the potential for generating new or additional SME business. Job creation is nevertheless limited at the current stage. However, the national Italian interest in food quality (and its communication) in an artisanal vs industrial narrative may lead to a good positioning of NUCs (broadly speaking) in emerging alternative food systems. This does not simply lead to room for manoeuvre in the food industry, but also in the catering and restauration domains.

Switzerland (LL LegItSwitz)

NUCs are an opportunity for small businesses to launch unique and differentiated products as part of a niche market. In the case of white lupin, these initiatives can also create job opportunities in bigger businesses as introduced above with the example of the the lupin coffee.

To conclude regarding this indicator, in some LLs (CerOcc in France, GPeaPort in Portugal), the use of NUCs started before DIVINFOOD, either traditionally (in Portugal) or more recently (CerOcc in France), and in both cases, contributed to the creation or development of small-scale businesses as a way to differentiate products and meet consumer demand for typical and/or healthy food. In other LLs, NUCs are also beginning to attract the interest of larger businesses, but often along a non-mild processing approach. This calls to assess the indicator in STEP2.

5.4 Consumers reconnection with primary production and biodiversity

What is valued:

Reconnection of consumers with primary production and cultivated biodiversity through NUCs consumption

The hypotheses are the followings:

- mild processing preserves the integrity of the NUC raw material, then facilitates the reconnection with the NUCs from which the product/dish has been made (knowledge increase);
- marketing in short chains, food festivals and tastings favour dialogue and consumer upskilling on NUCs and more largely, on cultivated biodiversity.

How to measure:

STEP1:

- YES/NO
- Ratio between the number of consumers knowing the crops/NUCs in the products/dishes they bought/ate in the LL and the total number of consumers buying/eating products/dishes in the LL

STEP2 - same ratios, applied to the LL region/country

Examples from DIVINFOOD Living Labs on the reconnection of consumers with primary production and cultivated biodiversity through NUCs consumption

Hungary (LL LegHung)

As introduced above, ACC in Hungary organised a community-based consumer evaluation with the seeds produced by the Leg-Hung LL, in cooperation with Agrikulti, between Jan-July 2024.

360 consumers subscribed to the tasting, the first 100 people received a small package of dry lentils, chickpeas and split peas (250 g/each) with Hungarian origin. Many of them discovered legumes they never used before. In this context, they also realised that most of the legumes sold in Hungary are not produced in the country and come from long chains. This was the opportunity to highlight the importance of local production and shorter chains.

Portugal (LL GPeaPort)

The focus NUC of the GPeaPort LL, grass pea, has contributed to a reconnection of consumers to its main national production region, Alvaiázere, now known as the “grass pea capital” in Portugal. Through a big dissemination effort from the local authorities (Alvaiázere Municipality) and local producers and processors association (ADECA), through an annual gastronomic festivity around grass pea since 2003, consumers from different parts of Portugal get in acquaintance, many times for the first time, with this NUC, a diversified offer of food dishes, and have the possibility to meet the local farmers and the local small processors in person, and to buy their grass pea seeds and food products, rediscovering an already lost biodiversity in many other regions of the country.

Italy (LL LegItSwitz)

The Italian part of the LegItSwitz LL is primarily revolving around farms in lower Tuscany and Lazio areas. Farmers are mostly interested in short value chains and in the territorial valorisation of white lupin, not least within the so-called ‘Food Community’ of Maremma (southern Tuscany), which promotes a local lupin landrace as part of the Community identity. The role of agrobiodiversity is maximised in this case, and it is/should be valued by consumers and citizens as a way to preserve territories and local traditions. The Tuscany Region is providing a viable policy framework and – as well as other Italian Regions – is managing a regional repository of cultivated biodiversity, acknowledging the role of ‘custodian farmers’. Cultivated biodiversity is then promoted to citizens and consumers, even if the real socio-cultural impact of it remains limited.

Lupins are seldom known in Italy as their cultivation is limited in a few areas: this implies local traditions that still persist, although at a limited scale, but also a large neglect in regions with no familiarity with the crop.

Switzerland (LL LegItSwitz)

In the Swiss part of the LegItSwitz LL, 42% of Swiss had never heard of lupin in 2022, according to an online interview. DIVINFOOD’s activity of this NUC helped to connect consumers to this NUC.

To conclude, regarding this indicator, DIVINFOOD’s activities created or strengthen opportunities to reconnect consumers with NUCs and agrobiodiversity. As a reference point, the European survey conducted at the start of the project revealed that, of the 1,699 respondents, only 39%

were able to name the plant species contained in the last meal they had eaten¹⁴. While the indicator in STEP1 would therefore certainly be low in most LLs, this calls to assess it in STEP2 in order to measure the impact of the value chains that will be developed and promoted within DIVINFOOD.

5.5 Diet nutritional value

What is valued:

The contribution of NUCs to diversify diets with healthy products

How to measure:

STEP1: Percentage of consumers who diversified their diets with healthy NUCs-based food in the LL

STEP2: % at the LL region/country level

Examples from DIVINFOOD Living Labs on the development of healthier eating habits through the consumption of mild processed NUCs

Hungary (LL LegHung and LL CerHung)

The most common motivations for Hungarian consumers to join the community-based consumer evaluation of the legume seeds produced by the LegHung Living Lab (see above) were as follows:

- 43% were interested in legumes, but did not have knowledge on how to prepare it,
- 39% were used to eat meat, but because of environmental reasons were open to eat less meat and consume more legume as a protein source,
- 38% liked to try out new food and recipes.

The 360 registered consumers received information on the legumes, participated on a webinar and received weekly newsletter on the topic. 98 consumers fulfilled the challenge and filled in an evaluation questionnaire after cooking the legumes received (a small package of dry lentils, chickpeas and split peas (250 g/each) with Hungarian origin).

In general, the initiative was positive: an increased legume consumption was reported thanks to the information and recipes they received. Most of the consumers (61%) chose the option to cook a main dish from legumes 1-2 times/week. Split peas and chickpeas were rated as the most popular legumes from the testing package.

¹⁴ Chiffolleau Y, Dourian T, Enderli G, Mattioni D, Akermann G, Loconto A, Galli F, Emese G, Perényi Z, Colombo L, Massari S, Desclaux D (2024) Reversing the trend of agrobiodiversity decline by co-developing food chains with consumers: A European survey for change, Sustainable Production and Consumption, 46:343-354, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.02.032>.

Furthermore, participants were asked to report on their legume consumption habits three months after the evaluation was carried out. More than 50% of the group said they were consuming more legumes than before the evaluation, diversifying their diets and probably reducing their meat consumption in a healthier eating habit.

The better nutritional quality of einkorn (*Triticum monococcum*) compared with bread and durum wheat lies mainly in the superior content of proteins (up to 19–21% under organic management), microelements and antioxidant compounds. The *T. monococcum* gluten content is comparable to that of modern tetraploid and hexaploid wheats, but its gliadin and glutenin allele composition displays an excess of gliadins over glutenins, leading to flours with very low gluten index and gluten strength. Nevertheless, einkorn flour is suitable for the manufacturing of cookies, unleavened foods and dry pasta. Finally, several studies are consistent with differences in einkorn gluten digestibility¹⁵, resulting in a lower content of immunostimulatory peptides involved in gluten-related disorders. Consumers including einkorn in their diets thus diversify their diets with an interesting NUC in matter of nutrition and health.

Portugal (LL GPeaPort)

Eating NUCs like grass pea is a way of adding legumes (and so plant-based protein) in the diet. This not only diversifies the daily diet, but also contributes to an adequate fibre consumption, and phytochemicals with potential bioactive effect such as antioxidant properties. The presence of these compounds regulates the levels of cholesterol and the body weight, preventing the development of non-communicable chronic diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus type 2 and colorectal cancer. See Table 1 below for more nutritional benefits of grass pea.

Benefit	Disadvantage	Reference
High protein content (largest source of protein next to soybean)		Mecha E, Alves ML, Bento da Silva A, Pereira AB, Rubiales D, Vaz Patto MC, Bronze MR (2023) High inter- and intra- diversity of amino acid content and protein digestibility disclosed in five cool season legume species with a growing market demand. <i>Foods</i> 12:1383. https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12071383
Rich source of lysine High glutathione and ascorbic acid content	Low sulphur-containing amino acids, cysteine, and methionine	Ramya KR, Tripathi K, Pandey A, Barpete S, Gore PG, Raina AP, Khawar KM, Swain N, Sarker A (2022) Rediscovering the potential of multifaceted orphan legume grasspea- a sustainable resource with high nutritional values. <i>Frontiers in Nutrition</i> 8:826208. https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2021.826208 .
High L-homoarginine content		Arslan M, Oten M, ErKaymaz T, Tongur T, Kilic M, Elmasulu S, Cinar A (2017) β-N-oxalyl-L-2,3-diaminopropionic acid, L-homoarginine, and asparagine contents in the seeds of different genotypes <i>Lathyrus sativus</i> L. as determined by UHPLC-MS/MS. <i>International Journal of Food Properties</i> , 20(sup1):S108–S118. https://doi.org/10.1080/10942912.2017.1289961
High folic acid content (vital to erythropoiesis along with nucleic acid and protein synthesis)		Ramya KR, Tripathi K, Pandey A, Barpete S, Gore PG, Raina AP, Khawar KM, Swain N, Sarker A(2022) Rediscovering the potential of multifaceted orphan legume grasspea- a sustainable resource with high nutritional values. <i>Frontiers in Nutrition</i> 8:826208. https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2021.826208 .
Source of Inositol phosphoglycan (used in traditional medicine to treat diabetic symptoms)		Pañeda C, Villar AV, Alonso A, Goñi FM, Varela F, Brodbeck U, León Y, Varela-Nieto I, Jones DR (2001) Purification and characterization of insulin-mimetic inositol phosphoglycan-like molecules from grass pea (<i>Lathyrus sativus</i>) seeds. <i>Molecular Medicine</i> 7(7):454-60.

¹⁵ Gazza L, Hidalgo A, Brandolini A (2023) A high protein ancient wheat species: Einkorn, *Journal of Cereal Science*, 114: 103790, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcs.2023.103790>.

<p>Beta-ODAP, up to 3% of the dry weight of a young seedling, has been applied as haemostatic agent following surgeries, reducing blood flow. It heals wounds naturally and in toothpaste can prevent bleeding gums</p>	<p>Beta-ODAP (causes muscle atrophy and lower limbs paralysis in humans, animals, and poultry) when poor diet exists. A combination of grass pea and cereals should be done in the context of a diversified diet to avoid neuro lathyrism.</p>	<p>Sharma D, Singh P, Singh S (2018) β-N-oxalyl-L-α,β-diaminopropionic acid induces wound healing by stabilizing HIF-1α and modulating associated protein expression. <i>Phytomedicine</i>. 44. 10.1016/j.phymed.2018.04.024.</p> <p>Enneking D (2011) The nutritive value of grasspea (<i>Lathyrus sativus</i>) and allied species, their toxicity to animals and the role of malnutrition in neuro lathyrism. <i>Food and chemical toxicology: an international journal published for the British Industrial Biological Research Association</i>. 49:694-709. 10.1016/j.fct.2010.11.029.</p>
<p>Beta-ODAP used for the stabilization of hypoxia inducible factor-1 (HIF-1)</p>		<p>Rathi D, Chakraborty S, Chakraborty N (2021) Grasspea, a critical recruit among neglected and underutilized legumes, for tapping genomic resources. <i>Current Plant Biology</i>. 26:100200. 10.1016/j.cpb.2021.100200.</p>

Table 2. Grass pea nutritional aspects

In addition, mild processing can contribute further to improve grass pea nutritional quality. Fermenting grass pea reduced the trypsin inhibitors activity (from 2.91 Trypsin units inhibited (TUI)/mg dry weight (DW) to 0.60 TUI/mg DW) and improved the antioxidant activity of grass pea (from 15.67, in raw, to 147.56 μ mol Trolox equivalent/g DW) (E. Mecha, personal communication). The fermented legumes can act as probiotic vehicles with positive impact in immune system and as products with extended shelf-life.

Italy (LL LegItSwitz)

Nutrition and quality drivers may be used to make NUCs less neglected in a plant-based dietary background, also arguing for more diversification in eating habits. In a very good example of this, FIRAB and DIVINFOOD are joining efforts with other groups and companies in the 2025 ‘Green food week’ campaign, led by the Foodinsider - an NGO dedicated to improving the quality of school canteens – that will promote lupins in the context of a greater attention to pulses in catering meals (not in schools, given its allergenic risk). Lupins is being introduced in menus for University's and private canteens meals on that week (7-11 April). The role of pulses and lupins will be promoted and disseminated through a rather intense communication plan, advocating the role of grain legumes in the framework of the ‘one health’ concept.

Switzerland (LL LegItSwitz)

Consuming NUCs and especially white lupin is beneficial to consumers to diversify their protein sources, especially due to their high protein content, rich in iron and satiety properties. The list of ingredients and level of processing are important criteria to consider in the diets too.

To conclude, the NUCs studied in DIVINFOOD have a high potential to diversify diets with healthy plant-based food, favouring a relative high level of the indicator in STEP1. This calls to assess the indicator in STEP2, to assess the impact of the products, recipes and value chains which will be developed and promoted in the project.

5.6 Attractive healthier diets

What is valued:

Consumers consider NUCs-based healthy products as attractive food products, and are more likely to adopt healthier diets

How to measure:

STEP1: Percentage of consumers who get a positive perception of NUCs thanks to the production and/or promotion of healthy, tasty and attractive NUCs-based products in the LL

STEP2: % at the LL region/country level

Examples from DIVINFOOD Living Labs on the increased attraction of healthier diets through the incorporation of NUCs

Hungary (LL CerHung and LL LegHung)

In the CerHung LL, pasta made with mild processing of NUCs (emmer, einkorn and spelt) have been tested with consumers. To increase the testers' knowledge on the topic, they had to participate in a webinar before the product tasting. The webinar was attended by 12 people, and others watched the recording afterwards.

After the webinar, a total of 25 people tested pasta made from the three types of cereals: spelt, einkorn and emmer wheat. The pasta was sent to them by post. They gave feedback on their experience through an online questionnaire. 23 people responded to the questionnaire. All these consumers were very happy with the opportunity and open to try similar new products and introduce them into their daily diet.

Most testers agreed that:

- all three pastas were easy to prepare (but spelt flour pasta was a bit harder to prepare)
- with shorter cooking times than the usual durum wheat pasta
- the texture was also very good, and didn't cook apart
- with einkorn and spelt pasta, consumers had a longer feeling of fullness than with the "traditional" pastas
- the einkorn and emmer pasta were very tasty, but the testers did not like the spelt as much (due to a "dry" taste)

On the other hand, discussions within the LL LegHung framework confirmed Hungarian consumers' aversion to legumes, highlighting many negative associations linked to their consumption. For example, one of the main aspects is that legumes can cause flatulence and bloating, and many consumers have had negative experiences with traditional legume-based dishes since childhood, particularly in school canteens (e.g. with a traditional yellow split pea stew). These negative stereotypes and associations could be countered with recipes and/or processing methods that recreate traditional recipes in a more tasty and appealing way, or by

creating new appealing recipes, or, if possible, by countering the bloating effect of legumes using various processing methods.

In addition, many people would find eating pulses appealing but feel that they do not have access to locally grown varieties or that these crops are not available in easy-to-use canned or frozen forms. Many consumers also find that cooking dried legumes takes a long time and is an activity they cannot fit into their daily routine. DIVINFOOD's activities create the opportunity to go in this direction.

France (LL BeanLyon)

In the LL BeanLyon, the first consumer feedback highlighted that bean consumption is usually linked to the image of bloated or gas feeling. But with meat bean, consumers reported that they are less bloated or have less gas feeling. Additionally, in a pastry recipe with meat bean, consumers appreciated the surprising taste as well as the chestnut flavour.

Portugal (LL GPeaPort)

Besides reducing the consumption of animal proteins to more sustainable levels, the inclusion of innovative fermented grass peas food products in diets may be seen as an attractive option to increase legume NUCs consumption. Fermenting grass pea allowed the development of volatile compounds such as furfural, 5-oxymethyl furfurole, responsible for sweet, nutty, and caramel notes in miso and 2,5-dimethylpyrazine, trimethylpyrazine and tetramethylpyrazine associated with roasted, peanut, cocoa notes in the tempeh (E. Mecha, personal communication). The presence of these compounds contributed to the development of sensorially attractive food products.

Italy (LL LegItSwitz)

Attractiveness is at the core of a Joint DIVINFOOD-Sexy Beans projects' initiative that was scheduled for mid-March 2025: in the context of the Sexy Beans project, design students coming from 3 EU countries cooperate with Italian design students on 4 different 'challenges' part of which around lupins promotion (either as product, process, communication...) and actual recipe elaboration. In this framework, one challenge will be launched by one LL lupin farm to better place lupin products on the market and one by FIRAB/Foodinsider on public catering. The results of the 'agile prototyping' explorations carried out by the students will be then in the hands of the challengers and we expect a good 'investment return'.

Grain legume NUCs benefits are often reported in magazines, conferences and layman initiatives. However, despite well-known nutritional and environmental advantages their consumption remains limited and unpopular. A greater effort should be made by health and nutrition institutes to increase consumption.

According to a nutrition researcher consulted in the project, it can be assumed that the microbiota used to regularly metabolise grain legumes in food regimes that have a constant intake of pulses leads to a reduction in fermentation (and flatulence) phenomena. This may contribute to dignify pulses as virtuous foods with virtually no side effects.

Switzerland (LL LegItSwitz)

No matter the benefits or the story behind the product, the final food product needs to be good enough (tasty) for consumers to get back to it. DIVINFOOD created or strengthened the opportunity to work with chefs, catering professional who valorise NUCs in well-known and tasty innovative recipes.

To conclude regarding this indicator, DIVINFOOD's activities are likely to increase its level in STEP1 thanks to the innovative attractive healthy NUCs-based products and dishes which are developed in the project. This calls to assess the indicator in STEP2 to assess the impact of the project in the next years.

6. Conclusion

From the surveys and discussions developed in the first years of the project, several indicators have been identified to document and follow the benefits of using agrobiodiversity in processing and eating. This deliverable report this set of indicators, which were expected to be easy to measure to facilitate a collective management and follow-up of agrobiodiversity use in European regions. Documenting and sharing these indicators is a key driver to encourage NUCs adoption by processors and consumers in Europe.

Other benefits of using agrobiodiversity appeared during the collection of data. For instance, the use of NUCs, as a non-routine activity, has been highlighted as an opportunity for small-scale processors to reappropriate the processing stage, and to give more sense to their work. DIVINFOOD partners need to remain attentive to all the benefits, and constraints, which will be emphasised by LL stakeholders. Finally, the possibility of reducing costs (processing or consumption) by using agrobiodiversity has not been sufficiently studied in this work package and will be explored further in WP5.

